
Service Organization Management and its Unique Features

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Abstract: The abstract summarizes the main concepts and importance of service management and also points out the critical factors for successful service management.

Key words: Customer satisfaction, quality services, efficiency, competitiveness.

In the conditions of the innovative development of the economy, the organizational and economic correct formation of the service sector is of great importance. Because the development of this sector is organizationally optimal and flexible to the conditions of the service market, the higher the quality and efficiency of service. Correct organization of work in the service sector will lead to the elimination of a number of social and economic problems at the scale of the national economy. Today, in our republic, "rapid development of the service sector, increasing the role and share of services in the formation of the gross domestic product, and fundamentally changing the composition of the services provided, first of all, at the expense of their modern high-tech types, is an urgent issue.

Management of service organizations is a complex process aimed at providing quality and efficient services to customers. In this process, it is important to take into account the specific characteristics of service organizations.

Service management is a complex process aimed at providing quality and efficient services to customers. This process focuses on identifying customer needs, designing, delivering and evaluating services, as well as continuously improving the service delivery process.

The main objectives of service management include:

Customer satisfaction: Services must meet customer needs and expected results.

* Quality services: Services should be of high quality and standards.* Самарадорлик: Хизматлар самарали ва тезкор тарзда етказиб берилиши керак.

* Competitiveness: Services should be designed to ensure competitiveness in the market.

* Team spirit: Team spirit of all employees involved in the service process should be high.

Key elements of service management include:

* Identifying customers: Identifying customer needs, expected results and requirements.

* Designing services: Designing services to meet customer needs.

* Delivery of services: Delivery of services in a quality and efficient manner.

* Evaluation of services: Evaluation of the quality and efficiency of services.

* Improvement of the service process: Continuous improvement and improvement of the service process.

The following factors are important for the successful implementation of service management:

- * Customer centricity: The needs and demands of the customers should be centered in the service delivery process.
- * Teamwork: Teamwork of all employees is important in the service delivery process.
- * Quality control: It is necessary to constantly control and improve the quality of services.
- * Innovation: It is important to use innovation in the service delivery process.

Technology: The use of technology to automate and improve the efficiency of the service delivery process is important.

Service management is an important factor for the successful operation of organizations. By applying the main elements of service management and taking into account the above factors, organizations can achieve customer satisfaction, increase the quality of services and strengthen competitiveness.

Management of service organizations is an important factor for customer satisfaction and organizational success. In this process, it is important to take into account the specific characteristics of service organizations.

Management of service organizations is a field of management that aims to organize, manage and ensure the effective operation of organizations engaged in the provision of special services. Service organizations differ from trade, production and other management models and have their own special characteristics and consistency.

In order to ensure the most efficient work of employees in service enterprises, it is necessary to study, improve service processes and develop comprehensively based service norms and determine the possibility of increasing labor productivity based on the effective use of working time.

However, there are factors that slow down and stop the increase in labor productivity even in the current conditions of the development of market relations. Because service enterprises are not constantly reducing their costs, increasing the volume of production and services, but using the scarcity and scarcity of the products they produce or the services they provide, and in exchange for increasing their prices, they achieve a planned amount of income. This situation, in turn, not only increases the further development of the uncontrollable inflationary process, but also makes it impossible to reduce the costs of organizing and managing the service process by widely introducing comprehensive scientific service norms.

List of used literature:

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